

EDUCATIONAL METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *The article highlights ways in which General secondary education schools improve the quality of education through the use of innovative techniques by an English teacher.*

Keywords: *school, innovation, pedagogical-technologist, method, education, upbringing, knowledge, skills, creative, classification, innovation, objective.*

ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В статье освещены пути, с помощью которых общеобразовательные школы повышают качество образования за счет использования инновационных методик преподавателем английского языка.*

Ключевые слова: *школа, инновация, педагог-технолог, метод, обучение, воспитание, знания, умения, творчество, классификация, инновация, цель.*

The advanced experience of pedagogy and the introduction into practice of achievements in education are considered one of the important conditions of today. Currently, a huge base of experiments has been formed that the teacher can use throughout his career, and he is getting richer every day. But despite this, the assimilation of these experiences by teachers and people of the future profession is somehow difficult. The position of an educator is especially significant in generating progressive experiences and popularizing them among their peers. The educator should pay attention to its value and to what extent it is effective in introducing a new advanced pedagogical experience into practice. The orientation of the practical activity of the teacher towards innovation provides an opportunity to put into practice the achievements achieved as a result of theoretical pedagogical research. It is in order to publicize the results of such studies that it is required to introduce them to the general public. Such innovations can be brought to other pedagogical Representatives by providing quick advice from specialists in the field, conducting special seminars and trainings, making speeches at conferences, and referencing series of lectures to future educators.

At this point, a question arises: "who are the promoters and promoters of advanced pedagogical ideas and technologies to representatives of the general public?». In the study, popularization of the experience of a separate educator or educational institution, professor teachers

of higher educational institutions, mature educators who carry out activities at educational institutions are important in this process. The reason for this can be explained as follows:

- the author of innovation cannot give the necessary and accurate assessment of the prospect of a particular pedagogical idea or innovation;

- advanced educators do not always think about popularizing their ideas. The reason is that the novelty requires additional time, labor of the educator;

- the idea is not always sufficiently scientifically-methodically substantiated by its creator;

- the authors meet the obstacles that are associated with the individual characteristics of themselves and their comrades in describing their innovations and ways of their introduction into practice;

- not only the promotion and popularization of pedagogical innovations, but also the task of enriching the professional erudition and skills of future teachers by making adjustments to the education of educators on their basis is also assigned to the creative team;

- the tasks of systematic selection of innovations, monitoring, assessment of innovative ideas, technologies, enrichment of work experiences of higher education institutions are also the responsibility of members of the creative team.

The author of the innovative idea does not participate in the management of activities aimed at application in practice. This style of approach sets the stage for expanding the capabilities of an innovative educator and directing him to a specific goal. The capacities of the founder and popularizer of innovative pedagogy are thus concentrated on one point and directed to a specific goal. Pedagogical innovation has its own specific dimensions. The main measure of innovative methods is their novelty, equal to the results of scientific research and advanced pedagogical experiments. For this reason, it is considered important for teachers who want to carry out activities in the innovative process to understand what the true essence of the innovation is.

While the experience being carried out is a novelty for a particular teacher, for another, this method may not be new. In addition, the novelty level of the same method for future educators can vary. With this in mind, both future educators and teachers working in the educational system will have to approach innovative creative activities based on their needs.

Innovative methods that promote the development of creative functions of future educators are manifested in several forms according to the degree of novelty: absolute level; local-absolute level; conditional level; subjective level. The use of innovative pedagogical innovations in public practice is interpreted as the norm of their assessment. This is mainly due to the technical support of the educational process and the specificity of the teacher's activities.

The creative application of pedagogical innovations in mass pedagogical experiments is

manifested at the initial stage of the work activity of individual teachers. These innovations are experimentally tested and presented for mass application after objective evaluation. It will be advisable to develop the creative functions of future teachers using innovative methods that will make it possible to achieve widely popular, positive results.

Diagnostic methods aimed at studying the innovative activities of the teacher are also colorful. The use of diagnostic methods demonstrates strong aspects of the teacher's activity.

Therefore, arming future teachers with modern methodologies of diagnosis is a period requirement. Taking into account the professional needs and desires of future educators, it is necessary to carry out full-fledged targeted activities aimed at the formation and continuous development of professional-pedagogical Ethics in them.

In the study of pedagogical innovation on the basis of diagnosis, one should not forget about the need to take into account that in each pedagogical experience there are positive, developmental situations, as well as negative manifestations. In order for a young educator to function effectively in an educational institution, it is required to clearly demonstrate on the basis of diagnosing the positive and negative aspects present in his work experience. It is necessary to accurately convey to the minds of future teachers that the diagnostic methods used for the purpose of studying innovative processes consist of the following.

- systematic study of pedagogical needs, interests, areas of special importance of future teachers, in which to identify the difficulties encountered in the activities of teachers and the possibilities of their elimination;

- search for ideas, concepts and advanced pedagogical experiences that serve to meet their interests and needs and introduce them into the practice of higher pedagogical education;

- specificity in the process of mastering and applying pedagogical innovations of future teachers and their diverse manifestations, such as the use of such types of work as demonstrating, describing, conducting open classes, working on new resources, organizing lectures, participating in pilot work, etc.

Practical work aimed at learning pedagogical innovations on the basis of diagnosis is also recommended to be carried out in several stages. From future teachers at the initial stage, questionnaire surveys, examination of the answers to the questions of the questionnaire, Organization of individual interviews and confirmation of the information in the answers to the questions of the questionnaire, analysis of the data obtained on the basis of the results of the diagnosis. At this stage, on the basis of the results of the first stage, activities aimed at improving the pedagogic skills of the future teacher are planned and the ways of their implementation are indicated. At this stage, the work carried out is completed and repeated diagnosis is carried out. In

this process, the future teacher is directed to obtain intermediate as well as final results. The changes that have occurred in the activities of students in the group are analyzed in depth. Thanks to this, the diagnosis of professional skills, qualifications and experiences generated by future teachers and their armament with diagnostic methods, as well as the reconstruction of the process of professional pedagogical education on the basis of innovative ideas make it possible to effectively develop the creative activities of students. Thanks to this, the opportunity arises to encourage future teachers to perform creative activities, to take initiative.

The creative pedagogical activity of the teacher is the process of positively solving tasks that are subordinated to the formation of human consciousness, behavior, and most importantly, the creation of a generation of harmonious people. Also, the designed training goal will be lightly realized and the expected result will be achieved faster. I.e.;

- in the system of innovative educational technology, it is necessary to clearly define the role and duties of the teacher;

- the teacher must be promoted to a new professional position - "teacher-technologist", - "educator-technologist";

- "teacher-technologist" must have special knowledge, skills, qualifications; -it is necessary that specific measures have been carried out between the pedagogical team of the "teacher-technologist" on the prestige, increase in potential, ensuring spiritual, material benefit.

In training in the development of the quality of education, teachers ' use of innovative technologies in the course of the lesson will certainly give effective results.

In conclusion, in order to educate mature specialists who have a high level of general-professional culture, social fauna, independent thinking, the ability to solve their tasks without difficulty, our educators today should understand that the use of modern new innovative pedagogical Technologies is the main factor in improving the quality and efficiency of Education, which the period requires.

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